

D6.4: Updated Communication and Dissemination Plan

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D6.4 Updated communication and dissemination plan

Due date:

31/03/2021

Actual submission date:

12/07/2021

Project start date:

01/01/2020

Duration:

M1-M36

Work Package concerned:

WP6

Concerned work package leader:

AEIDL

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Authors:

Lucia Princikova (Association Européenne pour l'Information sur le Développement Loca), Anna Pellizzone (Fondazione Giannino Bassetti), Angela Simone (Fondazione Giannino Bassetti), Marzia Mazzonetto (BE participation), Maïté Debry (BE participation), Diana Reinoso (Science for Change)

Revision history:

Version 1.0 (first draft): Lucia Princikova (Association Européenne pour l'Information sur le Développement Loca) on 09/03/2021

Version 1.1 (working document): Lucia Princikova (Association Européenne pour l'Information sur le Développement Loca), Anna Pellizzone (Fondazione Giannino Bassetti), Angela Simone (Fondazione Giannino Bassetti), Marzia Mazzonetto (BE participation), Maïté Debry (BE participation), Diana Reinoso (Science for Change)

Version 1.2: final version submitted on 31/03/2021

Version 1.3: revised version submitted on 12/07/2021 implementing modifications requested during the first project review process

Disclaimer

This report reflects only the authors' view. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N° 872687

Summary.

Regional research and innovation plans are key drivers for local regional development. By adopting RRI approaches to their R&I policies and actions, TRANSFORM aims to achieve more open, transparent and democratic R&I ecosystems within three regional clusters (Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital), leading towards more responsible territorial development. The implementing regional clusters will design, test and disseminate three methodological frameworks (participatory research agenda setting, citizen science, design thinking for social innovation) at the forefront of the implementation of their S3 strategies.

Through communication activities, TRANSFORM aims to improve overall general awareness about RRI and create a dialogue between institutions dedicated to territorial development. Through wide dissemination of project results, are dedicated to empowering diverse stakeholders to implement and/or engage with the development of RRI, promote shared learning and spread/share out of governance innovations.

The present Updated Communication and Dissemination Plan is instrumental to achieving the objective formulated above and is as such integrated into and supporting all the other activities of the project. WP6 works closely with other WPs to ensure two-way communication flows and sharing of information to maximise the impact of the project.

The TRANSFORM Communication and Dissemination Plan is a living document. This is an updated version of the initial Communication and Dissemination Plan submitted in M4. It provides an overview of communication and dissemination activities that took place until M15, progress in achieving the set KPIs and it also outlines next steps and activities. The Plan evolves over time, as a result of new or emerging information, opportunities or trends.

In the following sections, the key features of the Communication and Dissemination Plan are presented in detail, including:

- Communication objectives
- Stakeholder mapping
- Communication channels and tools
- Communication and dissemination products
- Quality Control, Monitoring and Reporting

Table of contents

TRANSFORM communication objectives	6
Communication objectives (COs) and key messages (KMs) Stakeholder Mapping	6
Stakeholder mapping	8
Regional Think Tanks	12
Multipliers	12
Related projects and initiatives	14
Communication channels and tools	17
Visual Identity	17
Website	17
Website structure	18
Technical development and maintenance	18
Search Engine Optimisation (SEO)	19
Social media	19
Twitter	22
LinkedIn	25
TRANSFORM social media main contents	27
Multimedia production	27
Videos	28
Photo shoot	30
Webinar	30
Media	30
Press release	30
Local/regional media	32
Events	32
Third party events	34
Communication and Dissemination products	41
Quality Control	44
Communication Team	44
Timeline	44
Guidelines	46
KPIs	46
Contingency Plan	47
Annexes	50
Annex I: Site Map	51
Annex II: Press release template	52
Annex III: EU Visibility Rules	54
Annex IV: Social Media Guidelines	56

Table of contents

Figure 1: TRANSFORM target groups	8
Figure 2: Website analytics - October 2020 - 12 March 2021	20
Figure 3: Website analytics: Visitors map	20
Figure 4: Website analytics - April - October 2020.....	21
Figure 5: Twitter analytics April - June 2020	23
Figure 6: Twitter analytics July - September 2020	24
Figure 7: Twitter analytics October - December 2020	24
Figure 8: Twitter analytics January - March 2021	25
Figure 9: TRANSFORM project animation – YouTube video analytics.....	26
Figure 10: TRANSFORM capacity building session no1: YouTube video analytics	27
Table 1: Targeted communication per audience	9
Table 2: Communication and dissemination partners of project partners	13
Table 3: Relevant projects/initiatives to explore synergies	15
Table 4: TRANSFORM-organised events	33
Table 5: Potential dissemination events	36
Table 6: Communication and dissemination products overview	42
Table 7: Communication team	44
Table 8: WP6 Timeline.....	45
Table 9: Key Performance Indicators	47
Table 10: Potential risks and mitigation results	49

TRANSFORM communication objectives

The core mission of TRANSFORM is to become an inspiring model of effective integration of RRI in territorial development, transferable to other regions.

Project objectives (POs)

- **PO1:** ESTABLISH a more open, transparent and democratic R&I ecosystems within three regional clusters (Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital);
- **PO2:** CONSOLIDATE Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) by integrating an RRI approach within existing regional innovation processes;
- **PO3:** EMPOWER diverse stakeholders to implement and/or engage with the development of responsible regional development processes and evaluate their impact;
- **PO4:** EXPLORE concrete R&I working methods based on three sound methodological approaches: participatory research agenda setting, citizen science and design for social innovation;
- **PO5:** ADVANCE territorial Responsible Research and Innovation by promoting shared learning and diffusion of governance innovations.

Communication objectives (COs) and key messages (KMs) Stakeholder Mapping

The Communication and Dissemination Plan plays a key role in supporting the project in achieving its objectives. In this respect, the Plan sets forth the following communication objectives:

- **CO1:** to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,
- **CO2:** to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;
- **CO3:** to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;
- **CO4:** to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;
- **CO5:** to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on RRI in territorial development, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximise impact;

- **CO6:** to widely disseminate TRANSFORM results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of TRANSFORM.

TRANSFORM's key messages are adapted to each target audience, as explained below. A set of messages is already proposed:

- **KM1:** Citizen engagement and participatory approaches contribute to openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.
- **KM2:** RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.
- **KM3:** Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (civil society, research and university, industry and public administration).
- **KM4:** Participatory processes in the regional R&I ecosystem represent an opportunity to actively involve civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.
- **KM5:** Citizen engagement as new form of governance represents an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by society.
- **KM6:** Concrete examples of responsible territorial development and tested approaches inspire and support regional authorities in transforming regional R&I ecosystems towards RRI.

Stakeholder mapping

Good communication is about giving the right information to the right audience at the right time and in the right format. Mapping all the relevant stakeholders and their interest is of capital importance to achieving the project’s objectives. The stakeholder mapping links target audiences with the communications objectives, as well as activities that will facilitate engagement. This detailed mapping allows for planning and design of targeted communication for each segment of the target audience from the onset of the project, and iteratively co-develop key messages. Based on this approach, the communications and dissemination activities will deliver maximum impact.

TRANSFORM identifies 6 specific target groups for communications activities illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: TRANSFORM target groups

The following table presents the stakeholder mapping for TRANSFORM and the communications objectives related to each of them. For each category, key messages, channels and goals are detailed in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1: Targeted communication per audience

Target audience (WHO?)	Communication objectives (CO) (WHAT?)	Communication Key messages (KM) (WHAT?)	Outreach channels (WHERE?)
Citizens and CSOs, NGOs	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p>	<p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (civil society, research and university, industry and public administration).</p> <p>KM5: Citizen engagement as new form of governance represents an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by society.</p>	<p>Social Media;</p> <p>Website;</p> <p>Dedicated public events;</p> <p>Partners channels;</p> <p>Videos;</p> <p>Promo materials;</p> <p>Final local events</p>
Public authorities (at all levels)	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p> <p>CO5: to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on RRI in territorial development, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximise impact;</p> <p>CO6: to widely disseminate TRANSFORM results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of TRANSFORM.</p>	<p>KM1: Citizen engagement and participatory approaches contribute to openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.</p> <p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (civil society, research and university, industry and public administration).</p> <p>KM4: Participatory processes in the regional R&I ecosystem represent an opportunity to actively involve civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.</p> <p>KM5: Co-creation and participatory approaches as new forms of governance represent an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by the society.</p> <p>KM6: Concrete examples of responsible territorial development and tested approaches inspire and support</p>	<p>Webinar;</p> <p>Project e-book;</p> <p>Social Media;</p> <p>Website;</p> <p>Final local events;</p> <p>Deliverables;</p> <p>Videos;</p> <p>Final conference</p>

		regional authorities in transforming regional R&I ecosystems towards RRI.	
Academia & Research	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p> <p>CO5: to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on RRI in territorial development, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximise impact;</p> <p>CO6: to widely disseminate TRANSFORM results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of TRANSFORM.</p>	<p>KM1: Citizen engagement and participatory approaches contribute to openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.</p> <p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (civil society, research and university, industry and public administration).</p> <p>KM4: Participatory processes in the regional R&I ecosystem represent an opportunity to actively involve civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.</p> <p>KM5: Co-creation and participatory approaches as new forms of governance represent an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by the society.</p>	<p>Webinar;</p> <p>Social Media;</p> <p>Website;</p> <p>Final local events;</p> <p>Project e-book;</p> <p>Deliverables.</p>
Industry & companies	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p>	<p>KM1: Citizen engagement and participatory approaches contribute to openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.</p> <p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (civil society, research and university, industry and public administration).</p> <p>KM4: Participatory processes in the regional R&I ecosystem represent an opportunity to actively involve civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.</p>	<p>Social Media;</p> <p>Website;</p> <p>Final local events;</p> <p>Press releases;</p> <p>Project e-book;</p> <p>Deliverables;</p> <p>Videos;</p> <p>Final conference.</p>

<p>Media</p>	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities, CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices; CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement; CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p>	<p>KM1: Citizen engagement and participatory approaches contribute to openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems. KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society. KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (civil society, research and university, industry and public administration). KM4: Participatory processes in the regional R&I ecosystem represent an opportunity to actively involve civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant. KM5: Co-creation and participatory approaches as new forms of governance represent an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by the society. KM6: Concrete examples of responsible territorial development and tested approaches inspire and support regional authorities in transforming regional R&I ecosystems towards RRI.</p>	<p>Social Media; Website; Press releases; Promo materials; Project events.</p>
---------------------	---	--	--

Regional Think Tanks

To ensure active and multi-stakeholder participation, each regional cluster engages relevant local stakeholders, representing the quadruple helix actors (universities, research groups, associations, CSOs, NGOs, science policy institutions, local businesses, formal and informal educational institutions, science mediators) with the aim of contributing to mapping, reflecting and action development. Think Tank members contribute to the activities carried out within each cluster by providing a variety of views, know-how and priorities, therefore ensuring that all societal needs are taken into account in the implementation of innovative solutions to responsible territorial developments.

Multipliers

This Strategy aims at achieving maximum impact with controlled spending by selecting channels that are the most effective in reaching out to the various target groups and **building upon multipliers**, namely consortium partners and relevant stakeholders at EU, national, regional and local level. Multipliers are invited to share the key messages, ongoing progress and ultimately the results of the project using their own communications channels, and tools.

Within the project partnership, the multiplier effect is ensured by the involvement of consortium partners that have a strong and well-structured presence at regional level, with widespread and multi-stakeholder networks. Furthermore, the regional focus is reinforced by involvement of regional Think Tank members.

At the European level, the multiplier effect relies first on the involvement of organisations and professionals, dealing with the topics of TRANSFORM, that are well connected with EU institutions and networks, as well as well-established European-level channels with which project partners have a good track record of engagement and participation.

The **Advisory Board** members, representing acclaimed experts in their respective fields, also support the dissemination of the results and maximise the visibility of the project. In addition, TRANSFORM consortium can count on strong support from local organisations and institutions that expressed their interest in the project by signing a Letter of Support (LoS). In total, the TRANSFORM consortium collected 45 LoS at proposal stage, including universities and research organisations, local authorities, private companies, business support organisations, umbrella organisations and associations, and other EU-funded projects. Consortium partners are regularly updating this list as new contacts emerge and other stakeholders are engaged.

Our goal is to **engage identified multipliers** to promote our ideas, convey our messages and help us better reach our objectives. Other multipliers include policy makers that have an umbrella function (such as EU institutions, National and regional authorities, EU Agencies) or are well connected such as international and national organisations (such as Civil Society associations, Intergovernmental organisations, networks and NGOs). In many cases, academia and independent experts can also act as multipliers.

Last but not least, cooperation of the European Commission will be sought for making use of the channels of EU institutions (e.g. EC, EESC, CoR, REA, JRC) and making links to EU CORDIS news and CORDIS WIRE websites, the Horizon Magazine, the Horizon 2020 Project Stories, newsletters from relevant DGs, etc.

Moreover, TRANSFORM takes advantage of existing channels of consortium partners. Partners activate their channels and networks to maximise outreach, visibility of the project, and communication and dissemination efforts

Table 2 below provides an exhaustive list compiled by all partners that offers an overview of other channels/tools that are used to multiply the content and outcomes.

Table 2: Communication and dissemination partners of project partners

Organisation	Channels
FGB	Website Twitter: @FGBassetti Facebook: @fondazionebassetti + Private Group: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti LinkedIn: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti + Group: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti Instagram: fondazionebassetti & IGTV Vimeo: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti Flickr: fondazionebassetti YouTube: FondazioneBassetti Issuu: fondazionebassetti Slideshare: FondazioneBassetti Newsletter (monthly; English and Italian) Podcast: "I dialoghi di Fondazione Bassetti" https://anchor.fm/fondazione-giannino-bassetti (also in iTunes, Google Play and Spotify)
BEpart	Website Twitter: @BeParticipation Facebook: @BEparticipation YouTube: BEparticipation
SfC	Website Twitter: @SciencefChange LinkedIn: Science for Change

UiB	Website Twitter: @vitenskapsteori Facebook: @vitenskapsteorl
UB	Website Twitter: @OpenSystemsUB Vimeo: Open Systems Flickr: OpenSystems
UCLouvain	Website Twitter: @UCLouvain_be Facebook: @UCLouvain LinkedIn: Université catholique de Louvain YouTube: UCLouvain - Université catholique de Louvain
Finlombardia	Website LinkedIn: Finlombarda S.p.A. Newsletter (monthly; Italian) Lombardy Region collaborative platform Facebook: @OpenInnovationLombardia Twitter: @LombardiaInnova LinkedIn: Open Innovation Lombardia YouTube: Open Innovation Lombardia
RL	Website Twitter: @RegLombardia Facebook: @Regione.Lombardia.official LinkedIn: Regione Lombardia YouTube: Regione Lombardia
GENCAT	Website Twitter @gencat Facebook: @gencat Instagram: @gencat YouTube: gencat Newsletter
Innoviris	Website Twitter: @Innoviris Facebook: @innoviris LinkedIn: INNOVIRIS
AEIDL	Website Facebook: @AEIDL.asbl Twitter: @AEIDL LinkedIn: AEIDL eLibrary (repository) Flash newsletter (bi-monthly; English and French)
MoS	Website Twitter: @museumofscience Facebook: @museumofscience LinkedIn: Museum of Science Instagram: @museumofscience YouTube: BostonMOS

Related projects and initiatives

TRANSFORM continuously seeks to build synergies with other relevant projects. Special attention is given to the EU-funded projects under the call [SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation](#), exploring potential synergies and cooperation in communication and dissemination activities, but also in other project activities such

as evaluation and monitoring, to maximise impact and foster peer learning. A non-exhaustive list of relevant projects and initiatives is provided in the table below.

Table 3: Relevant projects/initiatives to explore synergies

Project/Initiative
WBC-RRI.NET: Embedding RRI in Western Balkan Countries: Enhancement of Self-Sustaining R&I Ecosystems (H2020-SwafS-2020-1)
RRI-LEADERS: Leveraging Leadership for Responsible Research and Innovation in Territories (H2020-SwafS-2020-1)
RIPEET Responsible research and Innovation Policy Experimentations for Energy Transition (H2020-SwafS-2020-1)
<u>SeeRRI: Building Self-Sustaining Research and Innovation Ecosystems in Europe through Responsible Research and Innovation (H2020-SwafS-2018-1)</u>
<u>CHERRIES: Constructing Healthcare Environments through Responsible Research Innovation and Entrepreneurship Strategies (H2020-SwafS-2019-1)</u>
<u>DigiTeRRI: Responsible Research and Innovation Approach for Transitioning the Traditional Industry Regions into Digitalised Industry Territories. (H2020-swafs-2019-1)</u>
<u>RRI2SCALE: Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy (H2020-SwafS-2019-1)</u>
<u>TeRRitoria: Territorial Responsible Research and Innovation Through the involvement of local R&I Actors (H2020-SwafS-2018-1)</u>
<u>TeRRIFICA: Territorial RRI fostering Innovative Climate Action (H2020-SwafS-2018-1)</u>
<u>SUPER MORRI (SwafS-21-2018)</u>
<u>MARIE Project (Interreg Europe)</u>

Until M15, TRANSFORM project partners pursued the following actions in order to build synergies:

- FGB took part in the [Ricerca, innovazione e bene comune webinar](#) organised by **Art-ER** (one of the implementing partners of TeRRitoria project with activities in Emilia-Romagna, Italy), which took place on 25 September 2020. TRANSFORM and the citizen engagement methodologies explored in the project were presented during the webinar, followed by open discussion. The event was held in Italian as it was devoted to Italian stakeholders only, with around 100 participants.
- A capacity building session: [The methodology of the RRI Maturity Assessment at regional level: EU project MARIE](#) was organised with the objective to extract valuable knowledge and strategies that will help in the development of regionally co-created RRI evaluation tools in TRANSFORM. Presented by Giulia Bubbolini, the session was attended by TRANSFORM partners, and fruitful discussion followed. The recording of the session is also available in the TRANSFORM video library for wider audience to benefit from it.
- TRANSFORM (notably UiB), [SeeRRI](#) and [SuperMoRRI](#) created in June-July 2020 an initiative to exchange and coordinate experiences with RRI monitoring and evaluation across all SwafS-14-funded actions. This has resulted in dedicated workshops with all SwafS-14 actions and a

series of bimonthly regular meetings with SwafS-14 actions as part of the RRI ecosystem initiative of SuperMoRRI. UiB, FGB and BePart have taken part in these meetings.

- TRANSFORM (notably UiB) collaborates and exchanges updates on methodological development with [SuperMoRRI](#) on a regular basis, notably with SuperMoRRI WP5 leader IHS in Vienna.
- A bilateral meeting between TRANSFORM and [RRI2SCALE](#) coordinators (FGB and APRE) has been organised to discuss the chance to co-organise events in Italy on RRI and its implementation at national level.
- An initial contact has been made with [SeeRRI](#) and [DigiTeRRI](#) to explore a synergistic collaboration between the three projects for communication and dissemination actions.
- AEIDL is also exploring cooperation with [TeRRItoria](#) within the framework of #ResponsibleRegions - a series of monthly webinars organised by TeRRItoria. TRANSFORM could take an active role, as a speaker, in one of the upcoming sessions.

AEIDL is currently exploring a possibility to organise a joint session in cooperation with sibling project(s) within the framework of the European Week of Regions and/or European Green Week.

Communication channels and tools

The communication and dissemination channels are selected to convey the key messages and outcomes of the project to the largest possible number of stakeholders and target group members. The strategy works through both information pull and information push and will include various tools designed to reach different kinds of target groups.

Visual Identity

The visual identity was delivered in M6 and it has been consistently used since throughout various channels and products. Visual identity is at the heart of establishing a coherent and consistent image for the project.

The Communication Toolkit consists of:

- Visual style guide
- Logo (in various formats)
- Three cluster logos and one international partner logo (in various formats)
- Visual identity elements for website (Banner, video for banner)
- Social media banners (LinkedIn, Twitter)
- Templates for minutes and reports
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Template for WP deliverables

The project brochure providing an overview of the project in English was produced by M15. During the second year of the implementation of the project, three regional editions will follow providing more information on activities of regional clusters in Italian, Catalan, French and Flemish.

Website

www.transform-project.eu

The first version of the website was launched in M4, providing essential information about the project. The information was revised over time, and more pages were created as the project implementation progressed. Work on the website will continue throughout the project, incorporating sections and content according to needs. Technical maintenance will be ensured throughout the duration of the project.

The website serves as the first point of contact with the project for a wide audience, presenting its scope, activities and progress. At the same time, it represents the main communication and dissemination channel ensuring visibility and outreach, regularly updating the audience on activities within the project but also relevant news, documents and activities related to the topics relevant to TRANSFORM.

Design of the website is based on the following technical features and characteristics:

- A user-friendly and attractive interface, open to the public of potential users and different stakeholders
- Clear structure, easy navigation, evoking positive, encouraging emotions
- Optimised for all types of mobile devices (phones, tablets for both iOS and Android operating systems)
- Fully accessible by all users following the requirement for [W3C](#) compliance
- GDPR compliant, including all GDPR-related features (privacy consent for all forms, consent for cookies on a first visit, etc.)
- SEO-optimisation of pages
- Search facility on the site
- Offer a contact point
- Links to social media channels
- Web Analytics provided via [Matomo](#), an open-source platform with 100% data ownership and GDPR compliance.

Website structure

The website structure reflects the needs of the project, all work packages and partners while ensuring clear and intuitive navigation. To ensure the provision of information in a consistent and clear manner, all partners were invited to share their needs and vision on the structure of the website – a site map – presented during the kick-off meeting. The initial site map was slightly changed, based on the discussions and agreement among the partners. Annex I: Site Map presents a current version of the site map. Slight changes might still be applied, including the development of additional pages, subpages or elements, if needs arise throughout the implementation of the project.

Technical development and maintenance

The website was developed internally by AEIDL, coded using a leading content management system – WordPress. The website is hosted on the computer servers of AEIDL, allowing flexibility for web-development and dynamic functionality. The technical maintenance is ensured by AEIDL, content management – using an open-source Content Management System – lies fully under AEIDL with contribution from all partners. The content is regularly updated throughout the implementation of

the project. All partners' logos are clearly visible at the bottom of the website with links to their websites along with the EC logo and acknowledgment of the EU funds in line with the visual guidelines of the European Commission.

Search Engine Optimisation (SEO)

The website uses Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) techniques, with selected keywords, key phrases and extensive tagging to improve visibility. AEIDL plans to achieve high visibility for the website in organic search engine results by optimising pages with keywords - the terms users are likely to search on Google, Qwant, Yahoo and Bing (the search engines that currently generate the most traffic). To achieve this aim we deploy techniques such as writing keyword-rich page titles and adding description meta tags; include keywords in headers, positioning keywords in the first paragraph of the body text and using keywords in hyperlinks, etc.

Website analytics

To monitor the website analytics, Matomo analytics was installed in October 2020 as an ethical alternative without making privacy sacrifices or compromise the site. Matomo is the Google Analytics alternative that protects data and visitors' privacy, providing 100% data ownership. Before that, simple analytical tools provided by WordPress were used to monitor traffic on the website.

The graphs below provide an overview of website traffic until M15. We reached 3,891 visits with 90% of visitors coming from Europe.

Figure 2: Website analytics - October 2020 - 12 March 2021

Figure 3: Website analytics: Visitors map

Summary	
Summary	
Hits	
Total Hits	168,018
Visitor Hits	161,228
Spider Hits	6,790
Average Hits per Day	1,070
Average Hits per Visitor	54.60
Cached Requests	9,791
Failed Requests	1,856
Page Views	
Total Page Views	101,094
Average Page Views per Day	643
Average Page Views per Visitor	34.23
Visitors	
Total Visitors	2,953
Average Visitors per Day	18
Total Unique IPs	2,603
Bandwidth	
Total Bandwidth	1.51 GB
Visitor Bandwidth	1.42 GB
Spider Bandwidth	85.85 MB
Average Bandwidth per Day	9.83 MB
Average Bandwidth per Hit	9.41 KB
Average Bandwidth per Visitor	505.45 KB

Figure 4: Website analytics - April - October 2020

Social media

Various social media channels are used with the objective to increase the awareness of potential users, spark interest about the project and the topic of territorial RRI, and encourage them to take part in project activities, events as well as download the project's outputs. Each channel is intended to reach a specific audience, and the messages are adapted accordingly.

Social media is intended to act as an accelerator of the discussion; different social media channels will trigger snowball/networking effect and enable the project to reach beyond its 'usual suspects' audience. The various Social Media channels were set up for the project to reaching out to a wide and relevant audience. The content shared on each platform includes different types of outputs and redirects and feeds traffic to the main website.

Supporting visual materials are used in different social media channels in order to highlight messages. In general, appealing visuals help catch the attention of the followers/audience and invite them to read more and learn more about the proposed topic. For instance, video teasers/gifs shared on social media invite the target audience to read more. The illustrative elements, such as banners for social media profiles, help create brand consistency and visual identity for the project.

While we have initially foreseen to also open a Facebook page, after an internal discussion with consortium partners, we have decided to focus our efforts on two social media platforms – Twitter and LinkedIn. The reasoning behind is that even though Facebook is still popular among citizens and local communities, all regional clusters have extensive networks of their own that will be activated to

reach citizens and local communities and ensure their engagement in the project activities, moreover, addressing them in their national language. In addition, it has become rather difficult to build an active and engaged community on Facebook, especially within, and only for, a limited time of 36 months. Instead, Twitter account will help us to reach and connect with EU institutions, public authorities, industry, media, scientific community and EU-funded projects, maximising dissemination of the results and raising visibility of the project. Moreover, a LinkedIn group will be set up during the second year of the project implementation, inviting and bringing together EU-funded projects working on territorial RRI, relevant initiatives and key stakeholders to create a space to exchange and share knowledge, experience and lessons learned, explore synergies and foster networking. In addition, a specific [YouTube channel](#) was set up for the project, hosting videos created within the project.

The Social Media Guidelines were prepared by AIEDL and shared with partners to help them communicate about the project effectively and consistently on social media.

Twitter

Handle: [@TRANSFORM_eu](#)

Hashtags: #TRANSFORM #RRI #CitizenEngagement #SmartSpecialisation #StakeholderEngagement #delibwave #H2020 #SwafS #TerritorialDevelopment #Reseach #Innovation #CitizenScience #DesignThinking #ParticipatoryResearchAgenda

This channel is used for short news flashes, using a clear and crisp style, not too descriptive nor institutional. Twitter allows rapid communication between professionals, organisations and media. It is a real-time communication tool. It allows tweeting questions and having followers respond within a few seconds.

Although Twitter is less used in some European regions and on a local level among citizens, it is a major social media network used at the EU level within the European institutions, EU projects, umbrella organisations and international organisations. Thus, Twitter is mainly used to reach stakeholders at EU level, connect with other relevant projects and initiatives.

Offering only short messages – 280 characters – Twitter is known as a highly paced network demanding frequent activity and updates in order to maintain an active and attractive profile.

Retweets enable sharing of interesting content generated by other users as well as the possibility to easily spread messages to a wide audience.

Twitter is deploying key messages in a short, catchy manner using visual support (pictures, banners, infographics, short video clips, etc.) informing on the latest developments, news articles, publication of new documents, disseminating results and findings and promoting networking. Events are promoted via Twitter and pictures/videos and/or compelling quotes shared during the event. At the same time, it directs traffic to the project website.

As Twitter is a high-paced social media network, around 3-5 posts are published per week. The Twitter account was set up in April 2020. Until now (M15), TRANSFORM's Twitter account counts 324 followers and 241 tweets, therefore around 5 tweets per week. Twitter analytics show an increasing number of the followers as the project activities further developed, and consequently, more information and news is shared, and the wider community is being created around the project.

The number of impressions is increasing steadily each quarter, as well as the engagement rate (see Twitter statistic overview below).

Figure 5: Twitter analytics April - June 2020

Figure 6: Twitter analytics July - September 2020

Figure 7: Twitter analytics October - December 2020

Figure 8: Twitter analytics January - March 2021

We actively work on the creation of relevant connections thus contributing to widening the outreach of key messages. The Twitter account will be continuously used to communicate about the latest development of project activities, outcomes and relevant news.

LinkedIn

Group name: ‘Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation’

Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13853941/>

Being a social network for professionals, LinkedIn allows the creation of dedicated communities and groups to discuss specific topics and spread information to a wide professional audience. Based on this, a group has been created and will be used to connect with key stakeholders as well as relevant projects and initiatives to build synergies and foster knowledge transfer. Selected articles, news pieces and other communications content will also be shared on this platform. Via LinkedIn, TRANSFORM will host a permanent group (membership on request) community to create a space to foster exchange among its members, share experiences, events, studies, news and relevant information with peers.

The group will begin its activity during the second year of the project when the activities are further developed and more results are available. All projects funded under the H2020 call ‘SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation’ will be

invited to join and actively contribute to the group, and so will other organisations, professionals, initiatives and relevant projects. AEIDL will moderate and manage the LinkedIn group.

The frequency of posts published by moderators is foreseen to be once or twice per week.

YouTube

YouTube channel name: TRANSFORM project

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC0Tw8auUBj2MtQYMeX2OI-w>

A YouTube channel was created (M12) for TRANSFORM to host videos created within the project. Currently, there are two videos:

- Project animation – published 01/12/2020 (99 views, 102 impressions, 31.4% impressions click-through rate) – presenting the project and regional clusters to general public in a visually appealing and easy-to-understand format;
- TRANSFORM capacity building session no.1: The methodology of the RRI Maturity Assessment at regional level: EU project MARIE – published 9/03/2021 - (5 views, 16 impressions, 6.3% impressions click-through rate).

Figure 9: TRANSFORM project animation – YouTube video analytics

Figure 10: TRANSFORM capacity building session no1: YouTube video analytics

Due to the current situation caused by the Covid-19 global pandemic, TRANSFORM capacity building sessions are being organised online. We took this as an opportunity to make these sessions available for a wider audience. Therefore, all sessions are recorded and published via TRANSFORM's YouTube channel, also featured in a [video library](#) on the website and promoted via social media.

In addition, regional clusters are planning to create more project videos targeted at regional level in national languages. More details in *Cluster-specific communication and dissemination activities*. The final project video, summarising TRANSFORM's results and outcomes, is foreseen to be delivered in the third year of the project implementation.

TRANSFORM social media main contents

The above-mentioned social media channels will be used to maximise the visibility, dissemination and further exploitation (when possible) of the following content:

- Project objectives, activities and benefits
- Presentation of TRANSFORM partners
- Findings from reports and deliverables (storytelling style)
- Presenting clusters in depth – thematic priorities, commitments, S3 strategies, what they have been doing so far and activities developed within the project
- Presentation of used methodologies and their benefits
- Presenting mutual learning concept and cooperation with MoS
- Presenting TRANSFORM approach to monitoring and evaluation
- Showcasing good practices related to territorial RRI, especially those focusing on public engagement
- Promoting TRANSFORM events – Local final events and Final conference – What are they about? Why you should not miss them? How can you participate? Who is attending (presentation of speakers)? Join us!

- Sharing videos
- Promoting webinar and Project e-book
- Sharing interesting news from partners
- Disseminating public deliverables
- Promoting relevant EU, national, regional and local events
- Cross-promotion with other projects and initiatives
- Sharing relevant news, publications, training opportunities and events

Multimedia production

Videos

Animation

A short animation was developed and delivered in M11, published in M12. The initial duration was planned to be around 1 minute, but to cover the complete picture of the project presenting each cluster, we decided to go for a longer format – 2.22 minutes. The script was prepared by and agreed upon among AEIDL and cluster leaders, using an easy-to-understand, non-technical language and visually appealing form targeting a wide, non-technical audience. The animation includes ‘Call to action’ – Together for more open, inclusive and democratic R&I – and prompts viewers to learn more about TRANSFORM by visiting the website and join us on social media.

The animation was made in Adobe After Effects, it was made of a combination of bespoke vector images constructed in Adobe Illustrator, hand-drawn elements that were scanned and turned into vectors and stock photographs. The technical style of the video is known as 2.5D - this is where 2D images are positioned in 3D space, and a 'virtual camera' is created to zoom through this virtual space, creating the impression of true 3D via shifts in perspective lines. The video was exported as an h264 format MP4, in full HD (1920 X 1080), in 24 frames a second. This format was selected because it is very high quality but lightweight, making it easy and quick to transfer, upload and host.

TRANSFORM animation was selected for the virtual exhibition, showcased during the [3rd Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival](#), taking place from 6 to 12 December 2020, organised by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. The video is published on the TRANSFORM YouTube channel, as well as on the project website.

Capacity building sessions recordings

Due to current restrictions imposed by public authorities to halt the spread of Covid-19, capacity building sessions have been organised online via Zoom. We took this as an opportunity to record the sessions and make them available for a larger audience. The recordings are thus edited (adding introductory and closing slides) and published on the TRANSFORM's YouTube channel. A [video library](#) for capacity building sessions has been created on the project website, also providing a short overview for each session. The video library will be regularly updated as sessions take place.

Final video

Towards the end of the project, AEIDL will create a final video with inputs from partners. With a length of around 2 minutes, the final video will present testimonies of project partners (mainly clusters) and/or members of regional think tanks and organisations/citizens taking part in the co-creation exercises. The main focus will be on spreading TRANSFORM experience as a best practice, pointing out to the benefits of applied methodological approaches through the personal experience of participants. The video will convey a message to inspire local authorities, CSOs, NGOs, academia and companies to work together to implement RRI in their R&I activities. At the same time, testimonies of regional stakeholders and/or citizens will encourage participation in public engagement and co-creation activities. The video will put an emphasis on the TRANSFORM results – project e-book, strategic roadmaps – and the 'Call to action' will prompt viewers to use these results and implement RRI in their regional context. The visual identity of the project will be incorporated in the videos, ensuring consistency and coherence.

If the global health crisis caused by the pandemic of Covid-19 prevents face-to-face activities and meetings to happen in the second and third year of the project implementation, and we are not able to film project activities happening in person, we will find suitable alternatives to present project outcomes and lessons learned. An animation might be a suitable alternative.

Video will be published on the TRANSFORM's YouTube channel, shared on social media, be made available on the website, presented during events and further disseminated via the partners' channels and multipliers.

Photo shoot

Professional photos will be shot during project meetings and shared learning activities. These will also be used to produce short videos to be shared through project social media channels and website. Due to the pandemics, the first and the second project meetings were organised online and photo shooting in person were therefore not possible. Other activities will be put in place (e.g. video animation at the local level and other material to facilitate online engagement) and hopefully, the Consortium will meet in person in the second half of 2021 or in 2022.

Webinar

A webinar will be organised towards the end of the project (M35) to foster an interactive learning environment in which stakeholders feel involved. The webinar will present the outcomes and results of the project with a view to inspire other regions to take up the RRI approach in their R&I activities, provide guidelines and share knowledge on how to implement tested methodologies, draw attention to barriers, benefits and lessons learned. Ideally, this should eventually lead to further uptake of the project results and maximise its impact.

Media

The purpose of using general and specialised media content is to reach both the general public and a more specific audience with key information in the field of regional R&I, RRI and S3. We will use partners' existing media contact lists to develop and implement press and public relations activities. The subscription to Anewstip provides an extensive media contact database and allows the monitoring of news articles. The consortium will approach certain media to explore the possibility of publishing interesting news. Engaging with the press (from EU to local level) will be strengthened before the organisation of TRANSFORM events, in Brussels as well as in the implementing regions.

Press release

A press release is a statement distributed to the media to generate media/journalists' interest and thus press coverage on specific news. Press releases are written communication that should be issued when the project is doing something new, interesting, or different that would be of interest to local, national or European media. It is important to target the audience of the press release, keep it short and make sure that it has sufficient news value to compete with other news in a rather busy environment. When developing the press release it is vital to consider the audience. An audience analysis will determine the tone, style, angle and content of the article. Press releases also have an

impact on our future website's searchability, appearing in search results and encouraging media outlets to create backlinks to our site.

The first press release was launched via Anewstip on 16/03/2021 summarising the first year of TRANSFORM, its main achievements and next steps. AEIDL has curated a list of 827 recipients - journalists and media outlets covering EU27+UK based on the keywords search on topics covered by TRANSFORM (citizen engagement; responsible research and innovations (RRI), Smart Specialisation, public engagement; stakeholder engagement; citizen participation; deliberative democracy; deliberative wave, social sciences, democracy).

A press release will be also drafted for the key moments of the project (launch of citizen engagement activities by each cluster, before/after main events, when important milestones/results have been achieved or strategic deliverables are published, etc.). They will be drafted in a simple, effective communications language, and when relevant, they will be supported by infographics. Quotes of relevant speakers and participants will be included ad-hoc to personalise messages. The press releases will include the most relevant contact details to provide quick further information to journalists when needed.

They will be published on the TRANSFORM website and the partners' websites and advertised by social media links. The Press releases will be prepared by AEIDL in English and cluster coordinators will be encouraged to provide a translation in their national language (where relevant).

The press release template is provided in Word format in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** When writing a press release, it is important to follow the accepted press release structure and format, which includes:

- a headline;
- a sub headline;
- two or three paragraphs for the body;
- a boilerplate;
- contact information.
 - If possible, include contact details for potential interviewees (having their explicit consent for this) so that you make it as easy as possible for journalists to speak to/interview involved parties, as well as organisers.

Once it is filled in with the information, partners should remember to save the document as a PDF before printing it, sending it by email or publishing it on websites, social media, etc. By doing so, you will be sure to keep the exact layout

Remember that the press release template is a standard document to standardise the process at project level. However, you should consider tailoring the press releases to different publications, e.g. EU, national, regional, local, or specialist. If possible, include a sentence in each email to journalists explaining why the article will be a good fit for their publications/news outlet and interesting to their readers (the opening sentence). For example, if they have written a series of articles about public engagement, new forms of governance, etc., or have a section that focuses on R&I, think of mentioning that.

Partners should try to make their press release circulate as much as possible by:

- Sending it directly to their network
- Looking for relevant stakeholders working in their field and sending it to them
- Sending it to newspapers and local publications working on this topic
- Publishing it on their website

Sending it to AEIDL to publish it on the TRANSFORM website and to send it out through our Anewstip mailing list for TRANSFORM.

Local/regional media

The consortium will approach local media through an already established working relationship of local partners, especially local authorities, to maximise visibility at local level and reach a wide audience. Engaging with local media will be strengthened before and during the organisations of TRANSFORM events and when launching citizen engagement activities. AEIDL, in close cooperation with local partners, will continuously work on the identification of opportunities for local press coverage, including both online and offline channels.

Events

Table 4 provides a summary of the events organised within the project. In order to ensure effective communication and dissemination of the different actions, developments and results carried out, the table also details foreseen communications elements implemented during these events.

Table 4: TRANSFORM-organised events

Type of event	Objective	Target audience	Communication
Local Final Events M35	To present and disseminate the results of the project in each regional cluster; summarise and present the activities and outcomes; build a strong, long-lasting and engaged network beyond the duration of the project.	Regional and national stakeholders, Think Tank members, policy makers, CSOs, NGOs and public	Concept note Short article/Press release Social media campaign Direct email invitations Local/regional media Use of partners channels, EU channels and networks as multiplier to maximise outreach
Final Conference M34	To present a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project to a wider audience, increase the visibility of the project, create an opportunity for networking, foster the exploitation of results and maximise the impact. The emphasis will be put on presenting benefits of territorial RRI and transfer of knowledge fostering replication and inspire other regions to implement RRI in their regional R&I ecosystems.	Policy makers, CSOs NGOs Networks Other relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives	Concept note Short article/Press release Social media campaign Website news Direct email invitations Live Tweeting Sli.do Online survey Use of partners channels, EU channels and networks as multiplier to maximise outreach

Local final events

Towards the end of the project, each regional cluster will hold a final event to present the outcomes of the project and engage its local stakeholders. Targeting citizens, CSOs, NGOs, Think Tank members, policy makers, academia and research institutes, industry representatives and local/regional companies, local authorities, policy makers, and public, local final events will be also an opportunity to celebrate the successful implementation of the project, future plans and aspiration and establish and strengthen community building and public engagement.

Final conference

The final conference will provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project, serving to increase the visibility of the project, to foster the exploitation of results, and present it to the general public, target groups and relevant stakeholders. This international event is therefore targeted mainly at policy makers, CSOs and NGOs, with an expected attendance of at least 100 participants.

The details about the final conference (location, venue, organisation, specific themes and objectives, target audience and participants) will be laid out in a Concept Note to facilitate common understanding among partners. The monitoring and coordination of it will be undertaken by an event organisation team, led by AIEDL, in close cooperation with other partners. The final conference will take place in M34.

In case it is not possible to organise a conference with 100 participants, an alternative online format (online conference, a series of webinars/workshops, etc.) will be sought, discussed and validated by the partners.

Other TRANSFORM-organised events

In addition, AEIDL, in close cooperation with cluster leaders, will investigate possibilities to organise small public events/workshops/sessions on a local level in each cluster (Milan, Barcelona, Brussels). The events will be held on the occasion of further larger public local initiatives devoted to Research and Innovation (such as the European Researchers' Night, European Week of Regions and Cities) to reach a wider public and to communicate the project results in informal settings. AEIDL will coordinate the organisation of the activities. These events will take place towards the end of the project, once TRANSFORM can present and disseminate the results.

Third party events

TRANSFORM continuously identifies opportunities to actively participate in external events (conferences, workshops, etc.), targeting relevant domains for the project, to present the project, boost its visibility and disseminate results. Participation in events increases project visibility, facilitates networking and maximises opportunities for mutual learning, further uptake of project results and transferability. The impact of participation at this kind of event is very high because of the attendance of representatives of public authorities and policy makers. Workshops, meetings and other regional and EU events represent relevant and important opportunities for dissemination.

The goal of these events will be to communicate about the project and its activities as well as disseminate the preliminary results and share lessons learned of the project with TRANSFORM's target audience. The table below (Table 4) summarises the preliminary, non-exhaustive list of potential dissemination events attended by project partners.

In addition, AEIDL, in close cooperation with cluster leaders, will investigate possibilities to organise sessions within the framework of big umbrella events covering relevant topics (R&I, citizen engagement, circular economy, green transition, etc.), such as the European Researchers' Night, European Week of Regions and Cities, European Research and Innovation Days, Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival, European Green Week, to reach a wider public and to communicate the project results. AEIDL will coordinate the organisation of the event-related

activities. These events will take place towards the end of the project, once TRANSFORM can present and disseminate its results.

In the first 15 months since its launch, TRANSFORM partners participated in the following events:

Pint of Science Festival in Brussels: 'Shaping the city of tomorrow', 7-10 September 2020

- Organised by Pint of Science in partnership with Innoviris, the TRANSFORM project and BE Participation, the event first introduced the latest research on how cities can adapt to the environment and socio-economic challenges, while working better for and with citizens. TRANSFORM was presented on stage, and an interactive session moderated by BE participation allowed citizens to share their ideas on how to make Brussels city greener as part of a European Union-wide public consultation. The event was attended by state-secretary Barbara Trachte. The event had around 30 participants.
- **Ricerca, innovazione e bene comune webinar** organised by Art-ER, 25 September 2020
FGB presented TRANSFORM and the citizen engagement methodologies explored in the project during the webinar organised by Art-ER, one of the partners in the TeRRItoria project. The event was held in Italian as it was devoted to Italian stakeholders only, with around 100 participants.
- **European Week of Regions 2020, 'Shared agendas beyond EDP', 7 October 2020**
In the session dedicated to S3, EDP and citizen engagement, GENCAT presented "Coalitions for transformative change through shared agendas in Catalonia".
- On **17th November 2021**, FGB presented TRANSFORM in an online **workshop on science communication and citizen engagement** addressed to [Fondazione Cariplo](#) grantees.
- **3rd Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival, 6-12 December 2020**
- TRANSFORM's project video was selected for the virtual exhibition of citizen engagement projects available during the whole week of the Festival.
- **Research as a driving force for change in public policy: series of sessions on the interaction between politics and science and on collaborative research**, 4-18 February 2021. During the month of February, [the School of Public Administration of Catalonia \(EAPC\)](#) offered a series of sessions on the interaction between politics and science and on collaborative research. In the session "Collaborative research. How do we move from theory to practice? Methodologies, experiences and lessons learned" on 18 February, Sfc presented TRANSFORM and the citizen science methodology. This series of sessions was aimed at policy officers from Catalonia. Over 100 participants attended this specific session.
- UiB presented the TRANSFORM approach to RRI monitoring and evaluation at a **project webinar of MARIE** in February 2021.
- The TRANSFORM approach has been presented in webinars and courses in the Norwegian university sector, including the two national R&I centers called the [Centre for Digital Life Norway](#) and the [AFINO Centre for RRI](#), and a joint workshop with [Nord University](#) and [the University of Agder](#), for a total of approx. 60 participants; as well as in a webinar with the Austrian network for RRI, with approx. 15 participants from research organisations.
- On **3th March 2021**, FGB presented TRANSFORM in a **workshop on RRI** at Politecnico of Milan addressed to alumni and researchers and grantees of the initiative [Get it! Twice](#), promoted by [Fondazione Social Venture Giordano Bruno Dall'Amore](#).

- On the 25th March 2021, BEparticipation presented TRANSFORM and activities of the Brussels-Capital regional cluster during the workshop about the socio-ecological transition run by [POSECO](#). Around 15 participants, representing regional R&I actors, attended the webinar.

In addition, on the 6th and 8th of October 2020, FGB actively took part to the **stakeholder meetings** as well as to **LR General Directorates meetings** planned by LR and Finlombarda for the design of S3, presenting TRANSFORM project and bringing RRI and citizen' engagement in the process.

Due to the current outbreak of COVID-19 across Europe and measures implemented to halt the spread of the virus, many events in 2020 were cancelled, postponed or moved online. Taking into consideration the current situation, major EU events in 2021 are still planned online. We closely monitor the situation, update and identify the list of events during the regular communications meetings.

Table 5: Potential dissemination events

Name of event	Level	Date	Link
STS Italia Conference	National	17-19 June 2021	https://www.stsitaliaconf2020.com/
VIRI Meeting 2021/2022	International	Annual event (spring)	NA
General Assembly for research and innovation (Milan; 2021/2022)	Local	Annual event (summer)	NA
Public Communication of Science and Technology conference in Aberdeen	International	24 - 27 May 2021	PCST
Euroscience Open Forum 2022	EU	2022	ESOF
Meetings of the Citizen Science working group organised by Ibercivis and FECYT	Spain	To be confirmed	Citizen Science working group
Workshops of the working groups of the COST Action in Citizen Science	EU	To be confirmed	COST Action in Citizen Science

Annual Conference of the Science Technology and Society	EU	3-5 May 2021	STS Graz
Barcelona Science Festival	Local	Annual event, October	https://www.barcelona.cat/barcelonaciencia/en/13th-science-festival-1
ECSA Conference	EU level	Autumn 2022	https://www.ecsa-conference.eu/
UiB symposium	Local	NA	NA
4S meetings	International	NA	NA
EUSPRI Annual Conference	International	Annual event	https://euspri-forum.eu/
Eusea – European Science Engagement Association annual conference 2021/2022	EU	2021/2022	https://eusea.info/eusea-annual-conference/programme/
Ecsite annual conference 2021/2022	International	10-12 June 2021	https://www.ecsite.eu/conference
RSA (Regional Studies Association's) Annual Conference	EU	Postponed to 2022	https://www.regionalstudies.org/events/2020rsaannualconf/
European Research and Innovation Days	EU	24-26 June 2021	EU R&I Days
EU Green Week	EU	3 /5 – 13/6 2021	https://www.eugreenweek.eu/
European Week of Regions	EU	11-14/09/2021	https://europa.eu/regions-and-cities/
Citizen engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival	EU	December 2021/2022	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/event/conference/3rd-annual-citizen-engagement-and-deliberative-democracy-festival
I Love Science festival 2021/2022	National, Brussels	Autumn 2021/2022	https://ilovescience.brussels/en/homepage-en
Meetings of the ECSA HEALTH	EU	To be confirmed	https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/working-

			groups/citizen-science-for-health/
Citizen Science and SDGs Conference	EU	No dates yet	https://www.cs-sdg-conference.berlin/en/
CitSciVirtual: local, global, connected	EU	May 2021	https://www.citizenscience.org/events/conferences/citscivirtual/
European Development Days	EU	15- 16 June 2021	https://eudevdays.eu/
Science and Democracy Network annual meetings	International	No dates yet	http://sts.hks.harvard.edu/about/sdn.html
Society for Social Studies of Science - 4S Conference	International	6-9 October	https://www.4sonline.org/
Enterprise Europe Network services	EU	No dates yet	https://een.ec.europa.eu/
European Circular Economy Stakeholder Conference	EU	No dates yet	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/annual-circular-economy-stakeholder-conference-3-4-november-2020
Nuit européenne des Chercheur.e.s	EU wide event, incl. national event in Brussels	Autumn 2021 / 2022	https://www.sciences.be/evènements/ndc-europe/
Printemps des Sciences	National, Belgium	Spring 2022	https://sciences.brussels/printemps/
Semaine Européenne de la démocratie locale	EU wide event, incl. national event in Brussels	Autumn 2021 / 2022	https://pouvoirslocaux.irisnetlab.be/fr/theme/international/le-conseil-de-leurope/semaine-europeenne-de-la-democratie-locale

Cluster-specific communication and dissemination activities

Regional clusters are planning to develop communication, dissemination and outreach activities and products at the regional level to reach local citizens and stakeholders (academia and research institutes, policy makers and public authorities, CSOs and NGOs, media) in national languages.

The objectives of regional communication, dissemination and outreach activities and products are:

- To inform local citizens and stakeholders about the project and its activities taking place at the regional level;
- To engage citizens and local stakeholder (CSOs, NGOs, academia and research institutes, policy makers and public authorities, companies and industry) in regional activities;
- To disseminate project results at the regional level;
- To raise overall visibility of the project, the local partners involved, its activities and outcomes at regional/local level;
- To ensure the transparency of the citizen' engagement processes conducted at the regional level;
- To provide participants directly engaged in TRANSFORM's participatory exercises with all the relevant information on the citizen' engagement process;
- To increase the awareness around key TRANSFORM issues (i.e. RRI, citizen engagement, responsible S3 design and implementation, etc.).

Each cluster has designed a set of activities and products to reach these objectives.

Lombardy regional cluster

- Information material in Italian;
- Reporting video;
- A dedicated room on the Open Innovation Platform (a virtual space managed by Lombardy Region, where the Regional Government, industrial players, academia representatives and other societal actors can access information on Lombardy R&I ecosystem and can dialogue and interact), which will include all the relevant information on TRANSFORM project and citizen engagement process (i.e. TRANSFORM project description, Lombardy Cluster activities, participatory activities timeline, results and output, key documents to be shared);
- An online event at the end of the participatory actions (start of the summer 2021)

Brussels-Capital regional cluster

- Extensive mailing to representatives from Civil Society Organisations (non-profit organisations, associations) and other actors (academia and research institutes, policy makers and public authorities, companies and industry) to involve in cluster participatory activities and engage as multipliers to reach out a wider public;
- Short video presenting the participatory activities of the regional cluster with key actors concerned by the cluster pilot interviews;

- Communication campaign to reach out to citizens to engage in participatory activities, namely collective intelligence workshops to test circular economy innovations linked to the Brussels-Capital territory.

Catalonia regional cluster

- TRANSFORM brochure translated in Catalan and disseminated at regional level;
- TRANSFORM animation available with Catalan subtitles;
- Think Tank webinars & meetings: In 2020, the TRANSFORM [Catalan regional cluster](#) organised four webinars to foster knowledge exchange, open discussions and experimentations about RRI & citizen science. In this [series of participatory webinars](#), the TRANSFORM project was presented to the 55 Think Tank members - representatives from public administrations, research organisations and businesses of the Catalan R&I ecosystem. Three or four more sessions are expected to be conducted during the project's lifetime to disseminate pilot's advancements and the project's outputs. In addition, Think Tank members are regularly informed by e-mail about progress and outputs.
- A simple brochure of the health pilot is being designed to communicate the project to the citizens involved in the health pilot. A cluster is engaged in an ongoing discussion about designing and implementing a social media campaign (using the help of local influencers on social media) to engage more women in the project.
- A simple brochure of the pilot on waste will be designed to inform the target audience (for the moment, schools).

Communication and Dissemination products

Table 6 provides a summary of dissemination products developed within the project, including a short description, detailing respective target audience and dissemination channels deployed for each product

Table 6: Communication and dissemination products overview

Product	Description	Target audience	Channels
Promo materials	Brochures, leaflets, infographics, etc.	Citizens, CSOs, NGOs Local authorities Academia & Research Industry & Companies Media	Social media Website Events Media (articles, press releases) EC channels Partners channels
Audio-visual material (videos, images)	Due to the pandemics, the first and the second project meetings were organised online and photo shooting in person were therefore not possible. Other activities will be put in place (e.g. video animation at the local level and other material to facilitate the online engagement) and hopefully, the Consortium will meet in person in the second half of 2021 or in 2022. Videos (animation, final video) to present the project, its activities and impact in a visually appealing, easy to understand way.	Citizens, CSOs, NGOs Local authorities Academia & Research Industry & Companies Media	Social media Website Events Media (articles, press releases) EC channels Partners channels
Project e-book	An e -book will present the experimentation processes of all three clusters explored in the project, detailing used methodologies, strengths, weaknesses and practical hints to replicate the activities; an easy-to-use guide for policymakers and local stakeholders to implement RRI and participatory approaches in S3.	Local authorities CSOs, NGOs Academia & Research Industry & Companies Media	Social media Website Media (articles, press release) EC channels (Cordis) Partners channels
Webinar	An interactive webinar presenting the results with an objective to trigger more RRI approaches in S3.	Local authorities CSOs, NGOs Academia & Research Industry & Companies	Social media Website Partners channels
Strategic Roadmaps of the implementation of RRI in S3 through participatory research agenda/ citizen science/ design thinking for social innovations	An executive report, comprehensive of guidelines on the applied methodologies, to collect all activities carried out in Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital thanks to TRANSFORM will be finalised and released at the end of the process.	Local authorities CSOs, NGOs Academia & Research Industry & Companies	Website Social media Partners channels EC channels (Cordis)

Policy Recommendations to transforming regional R&I systems towards RRI	Inspiring regional governments and local authorities which would like to replicate transformative processes and implement RRI components within their R&I policies.	Policy makers	Website Social media Partners channels EC channels (Cordis)
Impact Pathways for RRI Initiatives in Regional R&I Ecosystem	A scientific publication that will disseminate the results from the assessment of scientific, environmental, economic and social impact pathways and benefits of TRANSFORM activities.	Academia & Research Local authorities Related projects and initiatives	Website Social Media Partners channels EU Channels (Cordis)

Quality Control

Communication Team

The WP6 'Sharing results and multiplying impacts', led by AEIDL, requires input and close cooperation with other work packages and project partners. Designing and implementing communication about the project and dissemination of results, its effective implementation is crucial for the success of the project. Therefore, the core communication team comprises of each WP representatives, and a wider communication team brings together one representative per partner

Table 7: Communication team

Team member	Organisation	Role
Angela Simone	FGB	Project Coordinator
Lucia Princikova	AEIDL	WPL
Christopher Murnaghan	AEIDL	Animation
Thomas Chullikal	AEIDL	Web development
Robin Salter	AEIDL	Video edition
Prody Mwemena	AEIDL	PR / Social Media
Anna Pellizzone	FGB	WP1, WP3 Lombardy cluster communication representative
Maïté Debry	BEPart	WP2, WP5 Brussels cluster communication representative
Diana Reinoso	SfC	WP4 Catalonia cluster communication representative
Kamilla Stølen	UiB	WP7 representative

Timeline

Table 8: WP6 Timeline

WP6: Sharing results and multiplying impacts																																					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
C&D Plan			D 6.1												D 6.4																						D 6.7
Visual Identity			D 6.2				D 6.3																														
Website			M 12																																		
Social Media			M 12																																		
Audio-visual material																																				M 15	M 15
Dissemination events																																					
TRANSFORM events																																				M 13	D 6.6
Webinar; eBook																																			D 6.5	M 14	

Guidelines

The Communication and Dissemination Plan aims at providing guidelines for the project partners to ensure consistency in all communication and dissemination activities and high quality of the materials produced within the project.

Guidelines intend to provide instructions, templates and recommendations for smooth performance, consistency and efficiency of all communication and dissemination activities and products. An initial set of templates, guidelines and recommendations are already included in this document's annexes. AEIDL will develop further templates, guidelines should the need arise during the implementation of the project.

- Site map (Annex I)
- Press release template (Annex II)
- EU visibility rules (Annex III)
- Social media guidelines (Annex IV)

In separate deliverables (D6.2 and D6.3), BE participation provided all partners with the visual identity manual and templates to ensure the homogeneity of all project outcomes

KPIs

Regular monitoring and evaluation activities will be conducted to measure gains and successes and provide information about progress with implementation, as well as lessons learned, and thus help revisit the overall objectives so that we do not get side-tracked.

All activities need to be measured and evaluated. The evaluation of qualitative and quantitative performance data gives insight that is needed to:

- optimise the Plan and ongoing activities;
- correct and fine-tune planning;
- make targeting more effective and therefore increase reach;
- improve activities and products;
- improve efficiency and minimise costs.

Metrics and dimensions from offline tactics (e.g. the number of Conference attendees) and their online equivalents (e.g. shared content on social media, number of followers, etc.) will be compared and correlated. This involves the processing and analysis of KPIs from all related communication activities and therefore from various systems, platforms and measurement methods.

Data are being collected from the following sources:

- Media monitoring
- Web analytics tools
- Social media analytics tools
- Post-event feedback forms

Table 9: Key Performance Indicators

KPI		Targets (M36)	M15
Website	Number of unique visits on TRANSFORM website	5000	3891
Social media	No of Twitter followers	500	325
	No of LinkedIn group members	200	NA
Videos	No of views	350 per video	100
Press release	No of press releases issued	4	1
EC channels	Frequency of use of EU communication services	2-4/year	1
Webinar	No of participants	30	NA
Project e-book	Number of downloads	50	NA
Local final events	No of participants	50	NA
Final conference	No of participants	100	NA
Events	No of presentations/active participation in third parties events	10+	13
Stakeholder engagement	No of quadruple helix stakeholders involved in local participatory activities	200+	Lombardy: 10 Catalonia: 60 Brussels-Capital: 36
Citizen outreach	No of citizens involved in local participatory activities	2000+	NA
Policy makers reached	No of additional regional governments engaged	8+	NA
	No of additional policy makers engaged within the same region(s) – different DGs, units, etc.	60	Lombardy: 30

Indicators of success will inform the progress towards achieving project objectives. The proposed KPIs below are guided by the European Commission (2015a) H2020 Programme indicators and aim to capture the achievements in communicating the project.

Indicators of success inform progress towards achieving project objectives. The proposed KPIs below are guided by the European Commission (2015a) H2020 Programme indicators and aim to capture the achievements in communicating the project. The above targets might need to be adapted according to the results of the internal evaluations of the Plan.

Ongoing cluster activities brought to our attention an additional KPI contributing to better reflect the impact of TRANSFORM activities. Within the KPI on policy makers reach, TRANSFORM will also look

at a number of additional policy makers reached within the same region(s) but from different units and directorates-general, bringing a wider institutional transformative change.

Table 9 above presents KPIs set at the beginning of the project and the progress achieved by M15. The data collected show that the project is on the right track to reaching the set KPIs. As some activities have not started yet, related KPIs are not available either. To reach the set KPIs, the following steps will be taken:

- Continuous promotion of the website; cross-promotion with other channels and activities (social media, events, etc.);
- Strengthening the engagement of partners, Think Tank members and other stakeholders as multipliers;
- Publication of relevant news and updates from the project on the project website followed by promotion via social media channels;
- Continuous social media activity and building community around the project;
- Press releases distributed following the major milestones of the project (e.g. launch of citizen engagement activities in three regions; publication of main deliverables; project webinar; TRANSFORM events);
- Production and promotion of project video(s);
- Communication, dissemination and outreach at regional level (Lombardy, Brussels-Capital, Catalonia);
- Identification and participation in events;
- Identification of opportunities to use the EC channels for communication and dissemination purposes;
- Organisation of regional final events and final event in Brussels;
- Exploring synergies with other projects, organisations and initiatives.

Inputs derived from the monitoring on the implementation of the Plan will feed into the project periodic reporting, scheduled for Months 18 and 36. The reporting and project reviews will assess project achievements compared to project plans and the Grant Agreement, and explain and justify any deviations from the plan. Linking to the findings of the interim reviews above, this deliverable will be subject to an update in month 18 to integrate any findings highlighted in the project interim reviews. Further modifications to the Strategy might be carried out to address urgent issues, as appropriate, in response to feedback gathered from the EC, the partners, and key stakeholders.

Contingency Plan

The contingency plan is implemented and monitored by the communications team, in close relation with the lead coordinator. It feeds the project's reporting duties when it comes to communication and dissemination, and ensures that proper and immediate follow-up steps are taken to mitigate or solve any issues that may arise.

Table 10: Potential risks and mitigation results

Risk for implementation	Level of Risk	Risk-mitigation measure
There is a gap between communication and the rest of the activities: partners are too focused on the specific WPs activities to get involved in communication, and tend to downplay obligations related to communications	Medium	Each partner has to nominate a contact person in charge of communications. A core communication team is set up to coordinate communication efforts with a representative from each regional cluster.
Project results are too complex to be communicated. Partners tend to focus on their own objectives and are not trained to identify effective messages to be communicated	Medium	The communication leader and co-leader will interact with the partners to identify the main messages. Partners will be encouraged to use the templates for an easier production. All products will be developed in cooperation with communications professionals.
Project fails to meet the target KPI values (number of participants during the events, social media engagement, number of posts, website traffic, etc.)	Low	In case of underperformance for a specific indicator, the communication team will devise a tailored plan with additional activities and measures to overcome these difficulties.
Lack of consistency of communications products (layout, language, etc.)	Low	Guidelines, quality control procedures and communications meetings will allow this risk to be overcome
Project events cannot take place in person due to external factors (global pandemic, etc.)	High	The consortium will work together on proposing and finding alternatives with suitable formats and agendas (online workshops, online conference, etc.)
Difficulties to produce planned audio-visual material due to restricted mobility caused by external factors (global pandemic, etc.)	High	Alternatives proposed by the WP6 team and discussed among partners to find suitable solutions (animations instead of real footage videos); other activities might be proposed instead.

Annexes

- Site Map (Annex I)
- Press release template (Annex II)
- EU Visibility rules (Annex III)
- Social media guidelines (Annex IV)

Annex I: Site Map

1. **Home** – opening banner, general info, clusters, news, partners
2. **About**
 - About TRANSFORM
 - Partners
 - Advisory Board
3. **RRI and S3**
4. **Citizen Engagement**
 - Participatory research agenda setting
 - Design thinking for social innovation
 - Citizen science
5. **Clusters**
 - Brussels-Capital
 - Lombardy
 - Catalonia
6. **Shared learning**
 - Resources
 - Deliverables
 - Publications
 - Photo gallery
 - Video
7. **News** (news and updates on project activities, press releases, events, etc.)

Annex II: Press release template

What's New?

The challenge here is knowing what happened. Your first step should be a catchy headline. Headlines should be short, but they need to grab the attention. You may also want to add a subheading with extra detail. After that, your first full paragraph should set out all the key information that you need to communicate. This can then be expanded upon in the next paragraphs.

Why Does This Matter?

What consequences does it have? Why do people need to know? And most importantly, what do you want to achieve by spreading this news? Keep it short and focus on these issues.

Who Are the Key Players?

Essentially, you may want to mention anyone for whom your news is relevant! In addition, press releases are most effective when targeted at a particular audience, so think about who you will send the press release to and who do you want to reach so you can tailor it accordingly.

When and Where?

If your news is specific to a time and place (e.g. a one-off event in a particular town), you will need to include this in your press release. But you also need to consider the timing of your press release.

The timing should be related to what you want to achieve. For coverage in the run-up to an event, send the press release 3-5 days before you want the news to appear (you can include an embargo to ensure it doesn't go out early). If you want coverage about something that has already happened, send it as soon as possible afterwards.

How Did This Happen?

This is about fleshing out your headline and opening paragraph by giving some background information. This might be for instance past instances of a similar event.

The key is to make this information quotable, and one way to do this is to include a quote in the press release. Include one key figure in a short sound bite.

If you can cover all these points, the content of your press release should be pretty much perfect. All you need to do now is write it up, get it proofread (for content and structure) and send it out!

SOURCE: Adaptation from <https://proofreadmydocument.com.au/writing-tips/5-questions-press-release/>

Annex III: EU Visibility Rules

Beneficiaries of the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme have the obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. This must be done, if possible and unless the Commission/Agency requests otherwise, in all communication, dissemination and IPR activities as well as on all equipment, infrastructure and major results funded by the grant¹.

The EU emblem and reference to EU funding must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence (taking also into account the nature of the activity or object). Examples: for equipment and major results a sticker or poster, for an infrastructure a plaque or billboard.

The following must be included in all dissemination activities (Article 29.4), communication activities (Article 38.1.2) and Infrastructure, Equipment, Major Results (Article 38.1.2)¹:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 972687.

When displayed together with another logo, EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This [e.g. report, publication, conference, website, insert type of result, etc.] reflects only the authors' view. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

¹ European Commission; H2020 Online Manual. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/acknowledge-funding_en.htm

Basic rules²

- The minimum height of the EU emblem shall be 1 cm.
- The name of the European Union shall always be spelled out in full.
- The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following:
Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana.
- Italic and underlined variations and the use of font effects are not allowed.
- The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem is not prescribed in any particular way but the text should not interfere with the emblem in any way.
- The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem.
- The colour of the font should be reflex blue (same blue colour as the EU flag), black or white depending on the background.

² European Commission; Use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes, 2012.
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/eu_emblem_rules.pdf

Annex IV: Social Media Guidelines

Social media can be a powerful force to share information, and we can only encourage the TRANSFORM team and partners to use social media in positive ways. When you are online posting about TRANSFORM or a subject linked to TRANSFORM:

- Disclose your relationship to TRANSFORM, for example in the Twitter profile;
- Use common sense when posting.

The **checklist** below will guide you when on social media and especially help you feel more comfortable posting about TRANSFORM.

	Share company stories, events, and career openings Share or retweet posts from the company's social media handles to be a vocal advocate for the organization. Be sure to use any hashtags suggested by the social media team.
	Publish or disclose confidential information Never publish confidential business information, such as sales leads, unaudited financial numbers, undisclosed revenue projections, etc.—electronically or otherwise.
	Be courteous and thoughtful; avoid getting into "flame wars" Share or retweet posts from the company's social media handles to be a vocal advocate for the organization. Be sure to use any hashtags suggested by the social media team.
	Respond to negative reviews on the company Do not independently respond to people who post negative reviews or comments about the business. The social media team should take responsibility for handling them.

Furthermore, here are some tips on how to efficiently post on your Twitter account.

- **Keep it short**

A concise Tweet makes greater impact. Keep each Tweet focused on one specific message rather than trying to communicate multiple things. You can include a link if you have a longer message to convey.

- **Use visuals**

Adding a bold image, video, or GIF to your Tweets adds a touch of personality, and leads to higher Tweet engagement rates. In fact, people are three times more likely to engage with Tweets that contain videos and photos. You can attach up to four photos to a single Tweet!

- **Incorporate relevant hashtags**

Hashtags are a powerful tool that allows you to expand your reach and tap into relevant conversations. Focus on keywords that are relevant.

- **Ask questions and run polls**

Don't be shy if you want to tweet in the form of a question. Asking questions is an effective way to interact with your audience, bring readers into the conversation, and understand people's opinions. Tweet open-ended questions or use Twitter polls to survey on specific responses.

- **Connect with Retweets and replies**

Retweeting relevant content and replying to Tweets are great ways to maintain a robust Twitter presence. When in doubt, remember this rule of thumb: your Retweets reflect back on you and should align with your values.

- **Make sure you are part of the TRANSFORM Twitter partners' list**

Twitter lists are a practical and useful way to monitor and interact with likeminded people. With this list all TRANSFORM partners will have direct access to what is posted on each other's Twitter account.

You will find below a style guide for your social media channels' use.

We hope this helps!

1. The style guide tl;dr (too long; didn't read)

The guidelines below will enable an effective way to publish content linked to TRANSFORM on social media. If you don't have time to read everything in this style guide, this first section can give you an overview:

- TRANSFORM's *voice* is friendly, approachable, genuine, and inclusive. The *tone* varies, based on the situation.
- Write succinctly, for the most part. Experiment with new features.
- Be thoughtful and intentional with the use of emojis, hashtags, and multimedia.

- Don't alter the spelling or punctuation of words in order to reduce the number of characters. Don't abbreviate beyond standard abbreviations (like "info" for "information").
- Don't use first-person singular pronouns, unless you're replying to someone (and your first name is included in your reply)

2. Voice and tone

Voice and tone matter: they will humanise the TRANSFORM brand and let you take part in conversations naturally.

TRANSFORM's voice is friendly, approachable, genuine, and inclusive.

Speak with clarity. Strive for expertise. Fully understand the needs of your followers and adapt content accordingly to deliver expert content, delight, assurance, or direction.

TRANSFORM's tone varies, depending on the situation

By default — and whenever appropriate — TRANSFORM's tone is friendly and positive. The way we speak encourages people to tell us more, and it invites people to get to know us. Because of this, try to take a conversational tone with written content: no big, dictionary words, just everyday talk that is easy to understand. We seek to inform rather than entertain.

3. Spelling, grammar, and punctuation

In general, keep social media updates crisp and to the point. Try to clearly communicate your point while being engaging

Main grammar takeaways:

- Use emoji on social media.
- Don't use emoji as punctuation or as a stand-in for vocabulary.
- Avoid gendered terms.

4. Emoji usage

Emojis can inject fun and personality into your social media! With TRANSFORM's tone being friendly and positive, emojis could become part of our social media culture. Although playful, emojis are an area that requires being thoughtful and intentional.

When and how to use emojis:

- **Twitter:** Use often and liberally in tweets and replies. Emojis can be especially great when used in place of bullets within lists.
- **LinkedIn:** Two emojis max or No emojis.

5. Hashtag usage

You can't talk about social media without talking about hashtags, they're important for everything from campaigns to joining in conversations. These will be particular to your subjects and you can include a list of campaign specific hashtags.

In the meantime, here is **a list of hashtags** you can use:

#RRI #SmartSpecialisation #CitizenEngagement #S3 #RIS3 #H2020 #SwafS #TerritorialDevelopment
#research #innovation #CitizenScience #DesignThinking #ParticipatoryResearchAgenda
#ResponsibleInnovation #OpenScience #RegionalInnovation #codesign #cocreation #delibwave

When and how to use hashtags:

- **Twitter:** No more than four hashtags per tweet.
- **LinkedIn:** No more than one hashtag per update.

6. Multimedia usage

- Use available templates.
- Try to use images of people that are as diverse as possible.
- Follow **visual identity guidelines** for colours and fonts.
- **Twitter:** Use Twitter size visuals to enable them to be properly visible on mobile. The ideal image size and aspect ratio are 1200px X 675px and 16:9, respectively. The maximum file size is 5MB for photos and animated GIFs.

7. Tagging, links

- Always tag **TRANSFORM** in all your posts.
- Tag project partners.
- Always try to direct people to the website, **add links** to your text with a **call for action...** *Learn more at... ; For more info... ; Apply here... .*
- Use link **(URL) shorteners** such as [bitly](#) .

www.transform-project.eu

 @TRANSFORM_eu

 TRANSFORM project group

 TRANSFORM project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N° 872687